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WORKSHOP: HOW DO TEACHERS RESPOND TO SUSTAINED CHANGE?

R. Hadgraft

University of Technology Sydney
Sydney, Australia

M. Rummler

Technische Universität Berlin
Berlin, Germany

F. Trede

University of Technology Sydney
Sydney, Australia

OVERVIEW

Higher Education is facing profound shifts, because employers seek graduates who can work effectively with others in rapidly changing, transdisciplinary contexts, defined by globalisation, digitalisation, sustainability, complexity and, most recently, a global pandemic. COVID caused an instantaneous acceleration to online learning (we often call emergency, remote learning), where academics were forced to conduct their normally face to face classes through video conferencing tools. The calls for sustained change are challenging academics to rethink their traditional teaching role.

This workshop seeks to understand how academics have responded to these challenges, both short term (emergency remote teaching) and the longer-term shift to transdisciplinary teaching, where problems in the world have become more complex and where graduates need to be prepared for transdisciplinary learning, working with diverse communities on their solutions.

BACKGROUND

In Australia, the Australian Council of Engineering Deans is currently undertaking a review of engineering education, the 2035 project. Its preliminary findings have identified the following changes in teaching practice will be required to: integrate real world situations in classroom teaching, integrate human/social dimensions of engineering problems, increase industry collaboration, use digital technologies and e-learning more effectively, and ensure professional development for engineering educators. We are keen to see how the European experience matches the current review in Australia and to explore the nature of professional development that will be required through this transition, towards more real-world, active learning.

PURPOSE

The purpose of this workshop is to collaboratively explore teaching experiences during the COVID pandemic and future engineering practice challenges, to gain

insights into the of future directions of higher education and engineering education in particular. All teachers will benefit from this interactive workshop. This session is an invitation to share ideas and think with others about the changing nature of their teaching and their other academic roles. This is particularly important as we reconsider how curriculum and teaching methods need to evolve in response to constant change.

With changing teaching methods, a more systematic academic development strategy will be required to provide academics with the teaching and facilitation capabilities for these new styles of learning. These capabilities include project-, team- and practice-based, integrative learning approaches. They require facilitation skills beyond what most academics experienced in their own university education.

ACTIVITIES

Participants will work in small groups to discuss three big domains:

1. Teaching changes due to COVID:

What have been the **positive and negative changes in your teaching practices** in the last 18 months due to COVID? How have these changes **affected you and your colleagues** as teachers? What have you observed about **student reactions** to this new form of completely online teaching and learning? **What are we learning** for the future of learning and teaching?

2. Preparing graduates for their professional future:

What do you see as some of the **big challenges** facing your graduates, in their lifetime? How do you see the **academic role changing** to prepare graduates for this increasingly complex world?

3. Supporting teachers for their changing role:

What formats, topics, and methods of **continuing education** would prepare you to become a more future-focussed academic teacher to prepare graduates for their professional engineering future in this constantly changing, increasingly more complex and uncertain world?

METHODS

The workshop will commence with a short overview of current developments in rethinking engineering education in Australia. We then intend to use the breakout room feature of the conference's videoconferencing tool, e.g., Webex. Participants will be divided into groups of 4 or 5 to give everyone more chance to speak. We are expecting 15-20 participants, so about 3-4 groups.

We will use a whiteboard tool that enables each member of the breakout room to post their ideas, thus accelerating the collection of ideas from a serial process of speaking and note taking to a parallel process of everyone being able to write at the

same time. We expect that participants will use one whiteboard per question (three in total).

In a workshop of 60 minutes, time is of the essence. We have broken this down to 10 minutes introduction and overview, 20 minutes of discussion in small groups, 20 minutes of reporting back to all participants highlighting key ideas, and 10 minutes for wrap-up. This method will give all participants opportunities to hear, share, and problematise the ideas generated in the other groups.

OUTCOMES

At the conclusion of this workshop, participants will have explored future trends in teaching engineering, with the intent of defining continuing education needs for those future skills. They will personally benefit from exchanging points of view and collectively developing didactic strategies for future transdisciplinary teaching.

The anonymous data gathered at the workshop will also help the workshop facilitators to shape an on-going research project: *Developing the Deliberate Teacher's Voice in the Age of Complexity, Sustainability, Globalisation, Digitalisation and Transdisciplinarity – how do Continuing Education Programs for Academics need to Change to Enhance Teaching Competence at University?*

ETHICS

We are currently applying for Ethics approval through our university's Human Research Ethics Committee, which will be finalised by the time that the workshop runs. We will ensure that the final version of this workshop description includes a clear statement of the intent of the workshop, which will specify that only anonymous data will be collected. Participation will be assumed as consent for the anonymous and ethically responsible use of the ideas generated.

RESULTS

In your opinion which are the most crucial positive and negative changes in your teaching due to Covid?

- Sense of urgency to adapt
- Social wellbeing came to the forefront
- Forced change made it possible to change but it is a double-edged sword because we might fall back to previous routines
- Realised that we ask so much of teachers: number 1 remains research and then making big changes in teaching without any support
- There was a clear difference between those who are good at adapting and experiment with different approaches and those who are reluctant to change
- Teachers are overworked and tired, longing to go back to more interaction
- Some people noticed that the teaching barriers were only in their head

What do you see as the big challenges facing your graduates?

- Responses related more to student learning than future world of work
- Lifelong learning
- Need for more hands on experiences
- Emphasis on personal development
- Lack of transferable skills

What formats, topics and methods of continuing education would prepare you to become a future-focused academic teacher?

- The discussion ranged widely from course team approaches to management and structural barriers
- Peer to peer learning
- Discussing change
- Creating space to tell stories and interact and share experiences
- Learning in hybrid systems, working in teams and experimenting together
- We only learn when we are present
- Rethink the conditions within which we have to work as teachers; setting up the right incentives
- In my university I've got the feeling that teachers are passionate about their courses and subjects but do not really feel part of a team. My feeling is that that is related that a lot of programs are not really a well designed curriculum but more a bunch of really interesting subjects joined together without cement
- I think our PBL helped to get teachers working more together
- I think our intentions to have peer supported development is sometimes undermined by the desire to be a 'leader' and seen as successful. Peer development requires openness around failure and not having individuals competing to be in charge of the group.
- The program perspective is lacking for many subject teachers. They see their discipline, but not the students' education.
- We need to encourage reflection in keeping good bits and integrating with previous models. Space to do that is important.
- I am struggling to get development time to be included in the workload model.